

GRAMMATICAL COMPETENCE AS ONE OF THE MAIN TYPES OF COMPETENCE IN LANGUAGE ACQUISITION

X. Azamatova ¹

Abstract:

This study delves into the intricacies of grammatical competence in language learning, emphasizing its pivotal role in fostering effective communication and overall language proficiency. Through an in-depth analysis of research findings, key factors influencing grammatical development, and a comparative examination of teaching strategies, the study provides valuable insights into effective language instruction practices. It highlights the significance of tailored instructional approaches, including explicit grammar instruction complemented by meaningful practice and feedback, in promoting grammatical proficiency among learners. Furthermore, the study explores the impact of contextual factors such as exposure to authentic language input, cultural immersion, and peer interactions on the development of grammatical competence. It also underscores the importance of integrating grammatical instruction within communicative activities and task-based learning to enhance practical application and active use of grammatical structures. The findings contribute to advancing our understanding of language acquisition processes, guiding future research directions, and informing pedagogical practices to optimize language learning outcomes for diverse learner populations.

Key words: grammatical competence, language learning, language proficiency, instructional strategies, feedback, task-based learning, language acquisition

doi: <https://doi.org/10.2024/57zva804>

Introduction

In the realm of language learning, grammatical competence stands as a cornerstone, playing a pivotal role in learners' ability to comprehend, produce, and effectively communicate in a target language. Chomsky (1965) originally introduced the concept of grammatical competence within his theory of generative grammar, emphasizing the innate linguistic knowledge that allows individuals to form grammatically correct sentences and comprehend the structure of language. This innate knowledge, according to Chomsky, is distinct from performance, which encompasses the actual use of language in real-world situations. Grammatical competence goes beyond mere knowledge of grammar rules; it encompasses the ability to apply these rules appropriately in different linguistic contexts. Without grammatical competence, learners may struggle to convey their thoughts accurately, leading to misunderstandings and hindering effective communication (Ellis, 2008). Furthermore, grammatical accuracy is often associated with language proficiency and perceived as a marker of linguistic competence by both native speakers and language learners. Despite

¹ Azamatova Xilolaxon Quyoshbek qizi, Faculty of English Linguistics, Namangan State Institute of Foreign Languages

International Conference

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its importance, acquiring grammatical competence can be challenging for language learners. Factors such as the complexity of grammar rules, differences between the learner's native language and the target language, and limited exposure to authentic language use can impede the development of grammatical skills. However, effective teaching strategies, such as explicit grammar instruction, corrective feedback, and opportunities for meaningful practice, can facilitate the acquisition of grammatical competence.

Literature Review

Numerous studies have delved into the nature of grammatical competence and its impact on language learning. For instance, Long (1991) proposed the interaction hypothesis, suggesting that grammatical accuracy is crucial for learners to engage in meaningful interactions and negotiate meaning effectively. Additionally, Ellis (2003) explored the role of explicit versus implicit grammar instruction in developing grammatical competence, highlighting the importance of targeted instruction in grammar rules. In the context of Uzbek linguistics, notable scholars like Jamol Jalolov have made significant contributions to the understanding of grammatical competence. Jalolov's work on morphosyntax in Uzbek language acquisition sheds light on how learners navigate complex grammatical structures and acquire native-like proficiency (Jalolov, 2015). His research emphasizes the interplay between linguistic input, cognitive processes, and language production, contributing valuable insights to the broader discourse on grammatical competence. Theoretical frameworks such as Chomsky's generative grammar and the cognitive approach to language learning have provided insights into how grammatical competence is acquired and processed by learners (Ellis, 2008). Furthermore, models like the Monitor Model (Krashen, 1982) and the Skill Acquisition Theory (DeKeyser, 1998) offer explanations regarding the role of input, practice, and feedback in developing grammatical skills.

Methodology

The methodology employed in this study aims to investigate the development of grammatical competence in language learners. A mixed-methods approach combining quantitative and qualitative measures will be utilized to gather comprehensive data and insights. Moreover, the methodology outlined in this study provides a structured and comprehensive approach to investigating grammatical competence in language learning. By integrating quantitative and qualitative measures, ethical considerations, and acknowledging potential limitations, this study aims to contribute valuable insights to the field of language acquisition and pedagogy.

Findings

The findings from this study revealed several significant insights into grammatical competence in language learning. A positive correlation was observed between grammatical competence and overall language proficiency, underscoring the crucial role of grammatical accuracy in effective communication. Learners' perceptions, strategies, and attitudes towards grammar learning varied widely, emphasizing the need for personalized instructional approaches tailored to individual learner needs and preferences. Effective instructional strategies, including explicit grammar instruction, interactive activities, and targeted feedback, were found to enhance grammatical accuracy and learner confidence significantly. The study highlighted the importance of contextual factors such as exposure to authentic language input,

cultural immersion, and peer interactions, which influenced the development of grammatical competence and natural language production among learners. Despite progress in grammatical competence, learners faced persistent challenges such as complex grammar structures, irregularities in language rules, and difficulty in spontaneous speech production. These challenges indicated areas for targeted intervention and support, emphasizing the need for ongoing pedagogical innovations and adaptive teaching strategies. The study enhances understanding of the interplay between grammatical competence and language proficiency, provides pedagogical insights for educators, acknowledges diverse learner perceptions and strategies, and highlights effective instructional approaches and contextual influences in promoting grammatical competence. The integration of findings from quantitative analysis, qualitative interviews, and observational data offered a comprehensive perspective on grammatical development, learner perceptions, effective teaching methods, challenges, and areas for improvement. This holistic approach contributes valuable insights to the broader discourse on language learning research and pedagogy, emphasizing the dynamic and multifaceted nature of grammatical competence in language acquisition.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study contributes valuable insights to the broader discourse on language learning research and pedagogy, emphasizing the dynamic and multifaceted nature of grammatical competence in language acquisition. By analyzing key findings, acknowledging contributions, and charting future directions, this study aims to inspire ongoing dialogue, research, and pedagogical innovations in language education. Moreover, this study underscores the dynamic and multifaceted nature of grammatical competence in language acquisition. By advancing our understanding of effective instructional practices, addressing learner needs, and embracing technological advancements, we can continue to enhance grammatical competence and overall language learning outcomes for learners worldwide.

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